

Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme (STP) on Knowledge and Attitude Regarding Menstrual Cup Hygiene Among Undergraduate Female Students

¹Hania Johansen Bhahama,
Nursing Officer 11 Nursing Incharge Cardiac
Operating Theater

²Dr. Uppu Praveen,
Associate Professor (HOD), Community Health Nursing
Sharda School of Nursing Sciences and Research,
Sharda University

³Chitra Diwakaran,
Assistant Professor, Obstetrics and Gynaecological
Sharda School of Nursing Sciences and Research,
Sharda University

⁴*Suman Pandey,
Assistant Professor, Obstetrics and Gynaecological
Sharda School of Nursing Sciences and Research,
Sharda University

⁵Asha Rani Morla,
Assistant Professor, Child Health nursing
Sharda School of Nursing Sciences and Research,
Sharda University

Corresponding Author:- ⁴*Suman Pandey,

Abstract:-

➤ *Background-*

Menstruation affects millions of women each month all over the world. This biological action is common. The majority of girls in lower and middle-income nations struggle to adjust to their monthly period because of societal pressures and a lack of advice, despite the fact that it is the most common biological activity.

➤ *Method-*

A Pre-experimental research design was conducted among 50 female undergraduate students of Sharda University Greater Noida, India. The participants were recruited by adopting purposive sampling technique. Data was obtained by self-administered questionnaire technique.

➤ *Result-*

There was a statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) difference found in the mean knowledge and attitude score.

➤ *Conclusion –*

Menstrual cups available for many years, still uses are very low. One of the main causes of poor uses is the lack of knowledge in maintaining hygiene of the cup. By providing appropriate knowledge regarding menstrual

cup will help to increase the adaptability of menstrual cup without causing any harm.

Keywords:- Menstrual Cup, Menstrual Hygiene, Knowledge, Attitude.

I. INTRODUCTION

Menstruation is a normal physiological process and a sign of healthy reproductive function. There are few options for controlling menstruation, and misunderstandings, prejudice, prohibitive costs, and safety worries may keep girls and women from considering all of their options.¹ Girls and women who are menstrual may leak and irritate due to a lack of affordable and effective menstruation products, which could harm their health.² Making use of poor materials Menstrual products for girls and women need to be effective, secure, and affordable.³

Studies have shown that improving menstrual health management in India requires educating women about MHM products, raising knowledge of the right use and disposal of sanitary absorbents, and regulating menstrual flow efficiently and hygienically.⁴ According to another survey, 62 percent of young women in India between the ages of 15 and 24 still cover their periods with clothing. Between 43 and 88 percent of the ladies still wash and reuse their cotton cloths as pads rather than using disposable ones.⁵ Therefore, maintaining menstruation hygiene is a

crucial yet underappreciated concern in rural communities.⁶ Menstrual protection in these countries is often provided by locally produced napkins and sanitary napkins, according to a prior report.⁷ A more recent development in place of sanitary napkins is the menstrual cup⁸.

➤ *Statement of the Problem:*

“A study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme (STP) on knowledge and attitude regarding menstrual cup hygiene among undergraduate female students at Sharda University, Greater Noida UP.”

➤ *Objective:*

To Determine the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on menstrual cup hygiene in terms of change in knowledge and attitude among female Undergraduate students.

➤ *Hypothesis:*

H₁: There is a significant mean difference found between pre-test and post-test knowledge and attitude score at 0.05 level of significance.

II. METHODOLOGY

To accomplish the objectives of the research, a pre-experimental research design was adopted to determine the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on menstrual cup hygiene on knowledge and attitude among undergraduate female students at Sharda University, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh. A total of 50 samples were recruited by adopting the purposive sampling technique. The data was collected in the month of May 2022.

Table 1 Comparison of Pretest and Post-Test Knowledge Scores of Participants Regarding Menstrual Cup Hygiene (n=50)

Knowledge Score	Mean	SD	MD	Paired t-test	P value
Pre-test	12.24	3.467	5.90	21.04	0.00
Post-test	18.14	2.935			

(p<0.05 significant level) S- Significant. SD-Standard deviation. MD- Mean Difference

Table 1 depicted that, statistically significant difference found in the mean knowledge scores of participants regarding menstrual cup hygiene between pre-test and post-test at p<0.001. It indicates that the intervention was effective in enhancing the knowledge of undergraduate female student. Hence researcher accepted research hypothesis (H¹).

Table 2 Comparison of Pre-Test and Post-Test Attitude Scores of Participants Regarding Menstrual Cup Hygiene (n=50)

Knowledge Score	Mean	SD	MD	Paired t-test	P value
Pre-test	29.08	8.02	3.16	4.20	0.00 (S)
Post-test	32.24	6.49			

(p<0.05 Significant Level) S- Significant. SD- Standard Deviation. MD- Mean Difference

Table 2 Depicted that, significant (p<0.001) mean difference found in attitude scores of participants regarding menstrual cup hygiene between pre-test and post-test at p<0.001. It indicates that the intervention was effective in improving the attitude scores of undergraduate female students. Hence researcher accepted research hypothesis (H²).

IV. DISCUSSION

The current study revealed that the intervention was effective in enhancing the knowledge of undergraduate female student and it was statistically significant, which was supported by a study was done by Maharjan S, et al. 9 Also,

➤ *Ethical Consideration:*

- *Administrative permission was taken from concerned Schools Dean to conduct the study followed by ethical clearance from Sharda University.*
- *Informed consent was taken from the participant. Participants were ensured that Anonymity and Confidentiality will be maintain.*

➤ *Tools:*

For the data collection, demographic Performa, questionnaire to assess the knowledge and rating scale to assess the attitude regarding menstrual cup hygiene were used.

➤ *Statistical Analysis:*

The data was organized in a master sheet and tabulated. The data analysis was done by using Statistical package EZR, version 2.4-0.

III. RESULT

Majority (66.0%) of the samples belongs to <20 years of age, most (70.0%) of participants had education of B.Sc, majority (80.0%) of them belongs to Hindu religion, most (96.0%) of participants were from urban area. Most (74.0%) of the participants were from nuclear family, majority (66.0%) of the participants family income were < 50,000, most (54.0%) of the participants age of menarche were from 15-17 years, majority (74.0%) duration of menstrual period is >28 days, most (68.0%) of participants length of menstrual period were from 3-5 days, majority (58.0%) of the participants they got information through parents.

it revealed that the intervention was effective in enhancing the attitude score (Favorable Score) of undergraduate female student and it was statistically significant, which was supported by a study done by Meghana S et al.10.

V. CONCLUSION

Menstrual cup is non-toxic, non-allergic and reusable silicone menstrual fluid collection device constructed of non-allergic and non-toxic silicon. Although menstrual cups are available for many years, still their uses are very low. One of the main causes of poor uses is the lack of knowledge in maintaining hygiene of the cup. By providing appropriate knowledge regarding menstrual cup will help to increase the adaptability of menstrual cup without causing any harm.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST –Nil

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